

ISic0434

Funerary stone of L. Licinius Daphnus

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. L(ucius) · Licinius

2. L(ucii) · l(ibertus) · Daphnus

3. vix(it) · a(nnos) · XXXV

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation (en)

Lucius Licinius Daphnus, freedman of Lucius; he lived thirty-five years.

Commentary

Origin unknown, but already recorded in Gualtherus 1624 (and as no.66 in the Palermo edition)

Digital identifiers:

TM 491662

EDCS 21900496

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7154 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650768>)

Gualtherus, G. 1624. Siciliae obiacentium insular. et Bruttiorum antiquæ tabulæ, cum animadversionib. Messanae. At no.228

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